

**EMBOSSSED NEMATODES FOUND IN AGROCENOSSES OF
SURKHANDARYA REGION**

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ANNOTATION: Embossed nematodes are a significant threat to the agricultural ecosystems of the Surkhandarya region. These nematodes have a major negative impact on plant growth and development. This article focuses on the studies conducted in the Surkhandarya region to understand the impact of embossed nematodes on crops and develop effective control measures. The main objective of this paper is to highlight the strategies for controlling embossed nematodes and promote sustainable agricultural practices.

KEY WORDS: Embossed nematodes, Surkhandarya region, agricultural ecosystems, soil health, crop rotation, biological pest control, integrated pest management.

INTRODUCTION

Nematodes are microscopic, worm-like organisms that can have a major impact on plant health. Embossed nematodes are particularly problematic in agricultural ecosystems as they can cause significant damage to crops. These nematodes are common in the Surkhandarya region, where they have become a major problem for farmers. The infestation of embossed nematodes has resulted in decreased crop yields and reduced economic viability of farms in the region.

MAIN PART

The impact of embossed nematodes on crops:

Embossed nematodes can cause a significant negative impact on crop productivity. These nematodes feed on the roots of plants, leading to stunted growth, reduced yields, and in severe cases, plant death. The infestation of these nematodes can

lead to a significant decline in soil fertility, as they remove nutrients from the soil. The economic impact of embossed nematodes is particularly severe for small-scale farmers who rely on crops for their livelihoods.

Control measures for embossed nematodes:

Several studies have been conducted in the Surkhandarya region to develop effective strategies for controlling embossed nematodes. One of the most effective control measures is improving soil health by increasing the amount of organic matter in the soil, which reduces soil acidity and boosts soil fertility. Crop rotation is another effective strategy that can help reduce nematode populations. Alternatively, farmers can use nematode-resistant crops or biological control agents to reduce the nematode population in the soil.

Integrated Pest Management:

Integrated Pest Management (IPM) is a holistic approach to managing pests and diseases in agricultural ecosystems. This approach involves combining different control measures to reduce pest populations and minimize their impact on crops. In the case of embossed nematodes, IPM strategies could include soil management, crop rotation, nematode-resistant crops, and biological control agents.

The natural conditions of the Surkhandarya region, warm climate, rapid development of agriculture, allow the cultivation of ecologically clean fruits, vegetables and berries. The fact that vegetable crops are grown in large quantities, the population's need for fresh vegetables allows to satisfy, to re-produce and export vegetable products. The growth of the gross vegetable harvest is mainly due to the increase in the number of greenhouses.

A total of 29 agroclusters are operating in Surkhandarya region. 13 of them are fruits and vegetables (production volume – 92,688 tons). In the region, 404.1 hectares of land are allocated for greenhouses by 122 farms, of which 5 of 45 hectares are hydroponic greenhouses, and 117 of them are greenhouses of 359.1 hectares.

In recent years, the volume of vegetable production has more than doubled, and at

the same time in greenhouses; 172 hectares of tomatoes, 63 hectares of cucumbers, 13 hectares of green peppers and 30 hectares of bell pepper are being planted. The yield of vegetable crops

One of the reasons for its decline is parasitic nematodes. Their harmfulness leads not only to a decrease in the yield of vegetable crops, but also to a deterioration in the quality of vegetable products.

Many scientific studies have been conducted on various agricultural crops in Surkhondarya region. Most of these studies were conducted in open fields.

Currently, the number of greenhouses has increased significantly, and conducting phytohelminthological research is becoming urgent. The purpose of this study is to study the parasitic nematodes found in vegetable crops and their distribution characteristics.

In 2021-2023, our research was carried out in the greenhouses of "Mustaqillik", "Limon", and "Sakhavat" neighborhoods of Termiz district of Surkhondarya region, "Khalqabad" neighborhood of Angor district, "Mekhrigiyoh" neighborhood of Muzrabod district, "Tong yulduzi" neighborhood, and several neighborhoods of Sherabad district.

The Berman method was mainly used to isolate nematodes from soil and plant samples. Males and larvae of root rot nematodes are isolated from the soil and the root system of plants by the Berman method, and females by the method of splitting the root tissue.

The research object is tomato - *Lycopersicon esculentum*, cucumber - *Cucumis sativus*, bell pepper - *Capsicum annuum* from vegetable crops in greenhouses in Surkhondarya region.

Collection of samples of vegetative organs of tomatoes and cucumbers grown in greenhouses, as well as the rhizosphere of the soil zone lasted for two years, during this period 240 samples were taken, isolated nematode samples were fixed in 15% formalin.

In the process of studying the nematode fauna of tomato, cucumber, and bell

pepper in vegetable crops in greenhouses, samples were taken from the underground parts of vegetative organs, the root system, and also from the root soil of these plants.

According to the results of our research, a decrease in productivity was observed as a result of serious damage to vegetable crops by nematodes. 80-100% of tomato and cucumber plants affected by nematodes.

CONCLUSION

Embossed nematodes are a significant problem in the agricultural ecosystems of the Surkhandarya region. The impact of these nematodes on crop productivity and economic viability is severe, particularly for small-scale farmers. However, effective strategies such as improving soil health, crop rotation, and biological control agents can help mitigate the impact of these nematodes on crops and promote sustainable agricultural practices.

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